

Study on Simple Symmetric Exclusion Process in Periodic Boundary Condition

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Abstract

In this project, we tried to figure out Dynamics of N-particles in Simple Symmetric Exclusion Process in Periodic Boundary Conditions, a model that exemplifies interactions between particles. Starting with a one-dimensional simple random walk, we delve into its mathematical formulation and physical implications. Then we extend this minimal model to an interacting one, where random walkers interact through hardcore repulsion. We investigate the behavior of multiple particles and their collective dynamics. By employing both analytical methods and Monte Carlo simulations, we analyze the temporal evolution and spatial distribution of particles in these systems. The findings provide insights into diffusion processes, correlation functions, and the emergence of non-equilibrium steady states. This comprehensive study not only enhances our understanding of random walk phenomena but also lays the groundwork for future research in non-equilibrium statistical mechanics.

Keywords: random walk, SSEP, Monte Carlo simulation, Diffusion

1. Introduction

Non-equilibrium statistical mechanics is a branch of physics that deals with systems, where there is current (e.g., of mass, energy, and charges), Unlike equilibrium systems, where macroscopic properties (averages of observable quantities) are time-invariant, it averages in non-equilibrium systems can exhibit temporal evolution and can be far from equilibrium. A fundamental concept within this field is the random walk, a mathematical model describing a path consisting of a series of random steps. Random walks are pivotal in understanding various physical phenomena such as diffusion, heat

conduction, and the spread of contaminants in a medium. This project delves into both simple and interacting random walks, exploring their mathematical formulations, physical interpretations, and implications. We begin by examining the one-dimensional simple random walk, where a particle moves randomly along a line, either stepping forward or backward with equal probability. This basic model provides insights into diffusion processes and forms the foundation for more complex studies. Next, we extend our investigation to interacting random walks, specifically focusing on the behavior of multiple particles. Interactions between particles introduce additional complexities, leading to fascinating phenomena such as clustering and collective dynamics. A significant part of this study is dedicated to the Simple Symmetric Exclusion Process (SSEP), a model where particles move randomly but cannot overlap. SSEP serves as a prototype for understanding exclusion principles in non-equilibrium systems. Through analytical methods and Monte Carlo simulations, we analyze the temporal and spatial evolution of particles in these systems. Our findings enhance the understanding of non-equilibrium dynamics and contribute to the broader knowledge of statistical mechanics. This study not only elucidates the behavior of random walks but also paves the way for future research in non-equilibrium statistical mechanics.

1.1. Simple random walk

Simple or one-dimensional random walk is one of the basic random walk concepts where $X_i = 1$ with probability p and $X_i = -1$ with probability $1 - p$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots$. Symmetric simple random walk means $P = 1/2$. Which means, flip a coin, take a step. If we construct a one-dimensional random walk, where one will walk along a line with each pace being the same length, he/she will flip a coin before each step. One step will be taken in the forward direction if it's head, otherwise one will take one step back.

1.1.1. Mathematics

Mathematically, a simple random walk can be defined as a physical process where a particle either move by $+1$ or -1 or stay at the same position. Suppose, a particle is at a position x at time t , after time $t + dt$, the position of the particle, $P(x, t + dt)$ will depend on 3 probabilistic situation, it may move to either $x - 1$ or $x + 1$ with probability p , or it can stay at the

same position, with a probability of $1 - 2p$. Which means,

$$P(x, t + dt) = \begin{cases} P(x - 1, t) & pdt \\ P(x + 1, t) & pdt \\ P(x, t) & (1 - 2pdt) \end{cases}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} P(x, t + dt) &= P(x - 1, t)pdt + P(x + 1, t)pdt + P(x, t)(1 - 2pdt) \\ \frac{P(x, t + dt) - P(x, t)}{dt} &= p[P(x + 1, t) + P(x - 1, t) - 2P(x, t)] \end{aligned}$$

If we do Taylor expansion on all of the functions of the right-hand side, we will observe that except second-order derivation, other terms will cancel each other. Which implies,

$$\frac{dP(x, t)}{dt} = p\Delta^2 P(x, t),$$

where Δ^2 is known as ‘‘Discrete Laplacian’’.

1.2. Continuous Approach

Now, if we apply the concept of coarse-graining, changing the parameters from x to Lx and t to L^2t , we get

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = p \frac{\partial^2 P(x, t)}{\partial x^2}.$$

Fourier transformation yields the following,

$$\tilde{P}(k, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P(x, t) e^{ikx} dx,$$

or, the inverse Fourier transform is given by

$$P(x, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{P}(k, t) e^{-ikx} dk$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{dP}{dx} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{P}(k, t) (-ik) e^{-ikx} dk$$

and,

$$\frac{d^2 P}{dx^2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{P}(k, t)(-ik)(-ik)e^{-ikx} dk$$

Putting all values in the original equation will lead to,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk \frac{d\tilde{P}(k, t)}{dt} e^{-ikx} &= p \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{P}(k, t)(-ik)^2 e^{-ikx} \\ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk e^{-ikx} \left(\frac{d\tilde{P}}{dt} + k^2 p \right) &= 0 \\ \left(\frac{d\tilde{P}}{dt} + k^2 p \right) &= 0 \\ \frac{d\tilde{P}}{dt} &= -k^2 p \end{aligned}$$

Integrating both sides gives,

$$\tilde{P}(k, t) = \tilde{P}(k, 0)e^{-k^2 pt}$$

Inverse Fourier transformation will give

$$P(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{P}(k, 0)e^{-ikx} e^{-k^2 pt} dk$$

Let's assume,

$$e^{-k^2 pt} = S(k, t)$$

So, Fourier transformation from S(k,t) to S(x,t) is

$$\begin{aligned} S(x, t) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S(k, t)e^{ikx} dk \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-k^2 pt + ikx} dk \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi pt}} e^{-\frac{1}{4pt} x^2} \end{aligned}$$

Using convolution theorem, we can turn the Fourier transforms into multiplication, therefore, to get the Fourier transformation

$$\tilde{P}(k, t) = e^{-k^2 pt} \phi(k) = S(k, t) \phi(k)$$

, we will use the convolution and we will get that,

$$\begin{aligned} P(x, t) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S(x-y, t)\phi(y)dy \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi pt}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{(x-y)^2}{4pt}} \phi(y)dy \end{aligned}$$

where,

$$\phi(y)$$

means initial condition or data, if we start our random walk from the origin, we will get,

$$P(x, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi pt}} e^{-\frac{1}{4pt}x^2}$$

which is a gaussian function.

1.3. Discrete Approach

In previous section, we have discussed about discrete laplacian, if we assume that the space interval is discrete for each discrete time step, we can express the equation from last section in discrete form,

$$\frac{\Delta P(x, t)}{\Delta t} = D\Delta^2 P(x, t)$$

Suppose,

$$P_i^n \rightarrow \text{Position after time step n}$$

$$P_i^{n+1} \rightarrow \text{Position after time step n+1}$$

Then

$$\frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2}$$

can be expressed in discrete laplacian,

$$\frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} \approx \frac{P_{i+1}^n - 2P_i^n + P_{i-1}^n}{(\Delta x^2)}$$

Put this in the equation,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{P_i^{n+1} - P_i^n}{\Delta t} &= D \frac{P_{i+1}^n - 2P_i^n + P_{i-1}^n}{(\Delta x^2)} \\ P_i^{n+1} &= P_i^n + D \frac{\Delta t}{(\Delta x^2)} (P_{i+1}^n - 2P_i^n + P_{i-1}^n) \end{aligned}$$

Let's take discrete Fourier transformation and rewrite the equation.

$$\tilde{P}_k^{n+1} = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} P_i^{n+1} e^{-2\pi i \frac{k}{N}}$$

and

$$\tilde{P}_k^n = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} P_i^n e^{-2\pi i \frac{k}{N}}$$

$$DFT(P_{i+1}^n - 2P_i^n + P_{i-1}^n) = \tilde{P}_k^n (e^{2\pi i \frac{k}{N}} + e^{-2\pi i \frac{k}{N}} - 2)$$

Using Euler's Formula,

$$e^{i\theta} + e^{-i\theta} = 2\cos\theta$$

We get,

$$e^{2\pi i \frac{k}{N}} + e^{-2\pi i \frac{k}{N}} - 2 = 2\cos(2\pi \frac{k}{N}) - 2$$

So,

$$\begin{aligned} DFT(P_{i+1}^n - 2P_i^n + P_{i-1}^n) &= \tilde{P}_k^n (2\cos(2\pi \frac{k}{N}) - 2) \\ &= -2(1 - \cos(2\pi \frac{k}{N}))\tilde{P}_k^n \end{aligned}$$

So, the equation will become,

$$\tilde{P}_k^{n+1} = \tilde{P}_k^n + [1 - 2D \frac{\Delta t}{(\Delta x^2)} (1 - \cos(2\pi \frac{k}{N}))]$$

Let's denote the continuous time variable as t and approximate this difference equation in a differential equation in a limit

$$\Delta t \rightarrow 0$$

Let,

$$r = 2D \frac{\Delta t}{(\Delta x^2)}$$

Now,

$$\tilde{P}_k(t + \Delta t) = \tilde{P}_k(t)(1 - r(1 - \cos(2\pi \frac{k}{N})))$$

Taylor expansion yields, (for small Δt)

$$\tilde{P}_k(t + \Delta t) \approx \tilde{P}_k(t) + \Delta t \frac{d\tilde{P}_k(t)}{dt}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{P}_k(t) + \Delta t \frac{d\tilde{P}_k(t)}{dt} &= \tilde{P}_k(t)(1 - r(1 - \cos(2\pi \frac{k}{N}))) \\ \text{or, } \frac{d\tilde{P}_k(t)}{dt} &= \tilde{P}_k(t) \left(\frac{(1 - r(1 - \cos(2\pi \frac{k}{N}))) - 1}{\Delta t} \right) \\ &= -r(1 - \cos(2\pi \frac{k}{N})) \frac{\tilde{P}_k(t)}{\Delta t} \\ &= -2D \frac{1}{(\Delta x^2)} (1 - \cos(2\pi \frac{k}{N})) \tilde{P}_k(t) \end{aligned}$$

Which is a linear ODE of the form,

$$\frac{d\tilde{P}_k(t)}{dt} = -\lambda_k \tilde{P}_k(t)$$

Where,

$$\lambda_k = 2D \frac{1}{(\Delta x^2)} (1 - \cos(2\pi \frac{k}{N}))$$

So, the general solution will be,

$$\tilde{P}_k(t) = \tilde{P}_k(0) e^{-\lambda_k t}$$

where the initial condition is

$$\tilde{P}_k(0)$$

Inverse discrete Fourier transform gives,

$$P(x, t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \tilde{P}_k(0) e^{-2D \frac{t}{(\Delta x^2)} (1 - \cos(2\pi \frac{k}{N}))} e^{i2\pi \frac{k}{N} x}$$

1.4. Monte Carlo Simulation of Random walk

In this section, we tried to approach the problem through Monte Carlo simulation and matched the analysis with an Analytical solution. At first, we have taken a random value of p between 0 and 1 in such a way that $1 - 2p \neq 0$. Now, we give a condition for the random walk, where we will generate a random number r between 0 and 1, if r is in range of $[0, p]$, the particle in random walk will do a left hop. if r is in range of $[p, 2p]$, it will do a right stop. it will stay in it's position if r is in range of $[2p, 1]$.

In Figure-1, we have taken the theoretical distribution alongside the simulation and tried to compare it, where we can see that for 100000 number of trials, we are getting a close match between the two curves. For simplicity, we have plotted the Monte Carlo time(a way to measure how far the simulation has progressed) to 100000 and have extracted the histogram data of the simulation, and binned the edges. From the extracted data, we have tried to plot distribution of final position in figure 2, $P(x, t)$ of the random walk for different time steps, for $t = 100, 200, 500, 1000$. Suppose, the Gaussian distribution has a mean μ with standard deviation σ , We can express the Gaussian distribution as,

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}}e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2}$$

Now, if,

$$\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right) = z$$

and,

$$f(x)\sigma = \phi(z)$$

Then, we will have,

$$\phi(z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}}e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}}$$

But, in our case,

$$P(x, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi pt}}e^{-\frac{1}{4pt}x^2}$$

where, μ is 0, so from the above equations, we can formulate,

$$\sigma = \sqrt{2pt}$$

Now, in Fig.3, we plot $\phi(z)$ vs z . From this we plot the deviation vs time graph for both simulation data and theoretical analysis in Fig.4, and we get a good match.

Figure 1: Comparison between Theoretical distribution and Monte Carlo Simulation for simple random walk of 100000 Monte Carlo time steps.

1.5. Simulation of Periodic Boundary Condition

In this case, we have taken a periodic boundary condition with length L and have done the Monte Carlo simulation. Starting from $\frac{L}{2}$, the probability of the right hop is p , and the probability of the left hop is also p with $1 - 2p$ probability of staying at the same position. But in this case, we have considered a periodic boundary, so at the rightmost point, if the particle does a right hop, it will transfer to the leftmost point. Similarly, a left hop from the leftmost point will transfer the particle to the rightmost point. We have simulated the Monte Carlo simulation of this condition, taking 100000 trials with 1000 steps. Now, we have taken different t values like $t = [100, 200, 500, 1000]$ and plot the distribution of the final positions of random walk. Now, along with this plot, we also generated another plot to find the steady-state time, for that we have generated the plot for $t \approx L^2$ and got this result in Figure 5. If we notice, the steady-state probability density at any given position should be $\frac{1}{100} = 0.01$. This is because for a domain of size L , the steady-state probability of finding the walker at any specific position is $\frac{1}{L}$. This is because, in a uniform distribution, each position is equally likely,

Figure 2: distribution of final position of the random walk for different time steps, for $t = 100, 200, 500, 1000$

Figure 3: $\phi(z)vsz$

Figure 4: Deviation vs time

and there are L possible positions. Hence, the probability density for each position is $\frac{1}{L}$. Now, for this physical condition, we have worked on Figure 7 and 8, we have also tried to find out the analytical solution by analyzing the random walk of a particle with periodic boundary conditions and derive the dynamics analytically.

1.6. Analytical Solution

Let p be the probability of the particle making a right hop. Let p be the probability of the particle making a left hop. Let $1 - 2p$ be the probability of the particle staying in the same position. Let's consider a one-dimensional lattice with N sites, labeled $0, 1, 2, \dots, N - 1$. Let $P_i(t)$ be the probability that the particle is at site i at time t . Then, the Transition Probabilities are:

- From site i , the particle can: Move to $i + 1$ with probability p or Move to $i - 1$ with probability p or Stay at i with probability $1 - 2p$ and the Master Equation will be as follows:

The probability $P_i(t + 1)$ at time $t + 1$ can be written in terms of the probabilities at time t :

$$P_i(t + 1) = pP_{i-1}(t) + pP_{i+1}(t) + (1 - 2p)P_i(t)$$

Figure 5: Distribution of final position of the random walk for different time steps, for $t = 100, 200, 500, 1000$ and $t = L^2$

Here, we use periodic boundary conditions:

$$P_N = P_0$$

$$P_{-1} = P_{N-1}$$

So the master equation becomes:

$$P_i(t+1) = pP_{i-1}(t) + pP_{i+1}(t) + (1-2p)P_i(t)$$

for $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1$.

To solve this, we can use the discrete Fourier transform. Define the Fourier transform of $P_i(t)$ as:

$$\hat{P}_k(t) = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} P_j(t) e^{-i\frac{2\pi kj}{N}}$$

The inverse transform is:

$$P_j(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \hat{P}_k(t) e^{i\frac{2\pi kj}{N}}$$

Applying the Fourier transform to the master equation:

$$\hat{P}_k(t+1) = p \left(e^{-i\frac{2\pi k}{N}} + e^{i\frac{2\pi k}{N}} \right) \hat{P}_k(t) + (1-2p)\hat{P}_k(t)$$

Simplifying:

$$\hat{P}_k(t+1) = \left(2p \cos\left(\frac{2\pi k}{N}\right) + 1 - 2p \right) \hat{P}_k(t)$$

Let:

$$\lambda_k = 2p \cos\left(\frac{2\pi k}{N}\right) + 1 - 2p$$

Then:

$$\hat{P}_k(t+1) = \lambda_k \hat{P}_k(t)$$

The solution in Fourier space is:

$$\hat{P}_k(t) = \lambda_k^t \hat{P}_k(0)$$

To get back to the probability distribution $P_i(t)$, we use the inverse Fourier transform:

$$P_j(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \lambda_k^t \hat{P}_k(0) e^{i \frac{2\pi k j}{N}}$$

If the initial condition is $P_i(0) = \delta_{i,i_0}$, where δ is the Kronecker delta (particle starts at site i_0), then:

$$\hat{P}_k(0) = e^{-i \frac{2\pi k i_0}{N}}$$

So:

$$P_j(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \left(2p \cos\left(\frac{2\pi k}{N}\right) + 1 - 2p \right)^t e^{i \frac{2\pi k(j-i_0)}{N}}$$

This is the analytical solution for the probability distribution $P_j(t)$ of the particle's position at time t given the initial position i_0 and the periodic boundary conditions.

To analyze the concept of the steady-state in the context of the solution derived for the random walk with periodic boundary conditions, we need to understand how the probability distribution $P_j(t)$ behaves as t approaches infinity. Follow Appendix A

2. Dynamics of N-particle in SSEP

The Simple Symmetric Exclusion Process (SSEP) is an essential model in non-equilibrium statistical mechanics that captures the dynamics of multiple interacting particles. In SSEP, each particle performs a random walk on a lattice, but with the crucial constraint that no two particles can occupy the same site simultaneously. This exclusion principle leads to complex collective behavior, significantly different from non-interacting systems. By studying the dynamics of N particles in SSEP, we can gain insights into how interactions influence diffusion, density fluctuations, and the emergence of non-equilibrium steady states. Analytical techniques, complemented by Monte Carlo simulations, help us unravel these dynamics, providing a deeper understanding of particle interactions and transport phenomena in constrained environments.

Figure 6: Monte Carlo simulation of N-particles dynamics in SSEP

2.1. Simulation

In this section, we have tried to generate a simulation, where, in a periodic boundary of a lattice size 0 to 100, we have confined n number of particles in a region around the mid position (50), 45 to 54, and let them diffuse over time, by following a symmetric random walk with p probability. Here, we have followed the exclusion principle, where, if a particle is about to do a hop, if the neighboring lattice site is occupied by another particle, the movement will be rejected, i.e., 1 particle can occupy 1 lattice site only. After simulating different time steps or t , we got a Gaussian-like profile. If we collect the simulation data, we will see that if we plot $\log y$ vs x , and we got a parabola, indicating the confirmation of the Gaussian nature of our simulation. Now, analytically, we have tried to approach this problem by treating the particle dynamics as a diffusion process and solving the corresponding diffusion equation.

The initial conditions are,

- Lattice length: 0 to 100.

- Particles are initially confined in the region 45 to 54.

- There are n particles in this region.

Now, We approximate the discrete lattice by a continuous interval $[0, 100]$.

2.2. Analytical Solution

To solve analytically, we will assume that if a particle is showing SSEP at lattice sites $i, i + 1, i - 1$ at time t , after time $t + dt$, the position of the particle, $\sigma_i(t + dt)$ can provide different outcomes based on different probabilistic situation, it may move from either $i - 1$ or $i + 1$ to i th site with probability p or q respectively, it can show vice versa of this dynamics or it can stay at the same position, Which means,

$$\sigma_i(t + dt) = \begin{cases} 1 & p\sigma_{i-1}(1 - \sigma_i)dt \\ 1 & q\sigma_{i+1}(1 - \sigma_i)dt \\ 0 & p\sigma_i(1 - \sigma_{i+1})dt \\ 0 & q\sigma_i(1 - \sigma_{i-1})dt \\ \sigma_i(t) & otherwise \end{cases}$$

Therefore,

$$\langle \sigma_i(t + dt) \rangle = p\langle \sigma_{i-1}(1 - \sigma_i) \rangle dt + q\langle \sigma_{i+1}(1 - \sigma_i) \rangle dt + \langle \sigma_i(t)(1 - p\sigma_{i-1}(1 - \sigma_i)dt - \dots) \rangle$$

Simplification yields,

$$\frac{d}{dt} \langle \sigma_i \rangle = (p\langle \sigma_{i-1} \rangle + q\langle \sigma_{i+1} \rangle - (p + q)\langle \sigma_i \rangle) + (p - q)(\langle \sigma_{i+1}\sigma_i \rangle - \langle \sigma_i\sigma_{i-1} \rangle)$$

But, in case of SSEP, $p = q$ to keep the process symmetric, which will lead us to

$$\frac{d}{dt} \langle \sigma_i \rangle = p(\langle \sigma_{i+1} \rangle + \langle \sigma_{i-1} \rangle - 2\langle \sigma_i \rangle)$$

Using Taylor expansion around x :

$$\rho(x \pm \Delta x, t) \approx \rho(x, t) \pm \Delta x \frac{\partial \rho(x, t)}{\partial x} + \frac{(\Delta x)^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \rho(x, t)}{\partial x^2} + \mathcal{O}((\Delta x)^3)$$

Substitute this into the discrete equation:

$$\langle \sigma_{i+1} \rangle + \langle \sigma_{i-1} \rangle \approx \rho(x + \Delta x, t) + \rho(x - \Delta x, t)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\approx \left[\rho(x, t) + \Delta x \frac{\partial \rho(x, t)}{\partial x} + \frac{(\Delta x)^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \rho(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \right] + \left[\rho(x, t) - \Delta x \frac{\partial \rho(x, t)}{\partial x} + \frac{(\Delta x)^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \rho(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \right] \\ &= 2\rho(x, t) + (\Delta x)^2 \frac{\partial^2 \rho(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \end{aligned}$$

The discrete equation becomes:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \langle \sigma_i \rangle = p(2\rho(x, t) + (\Delta x)^2 \frac{\partial^2 \rho(x, t)}{\partial x^2} - 2\rho(x, t))$$

Simplify it:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \rho(x, t) = p(\Delta x)^2 \frac{\partial^2 \rho(x, t)}{\partial x^2}$$

Now, define the diffusion coefficient D as $p(\Delta x)^2$:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \rho(x, t) = D \frac{\partial^2 \rho(x, t)}{\partial x^2}$$

Rewriting it in the standard form of the diffusion equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho(x, t)}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 \rho(x, t)}{\partial x^2}$$

which gives us a form of the diffusion equation with diffusion coefficient $D = p(\Delta x)^2$. The transition shows how the microscopic random walk leads to macroscopic diffusion behavior, consistent with the central limit theorem and Gaussian distributions at large times.

So, The dynamics of particles can be described by the diffusion equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho(x, t)}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 \rho(x, t)}{\partial x^2}$$

where $\rho(x, t)$ is the particle density at position x and time t , and D is the diffusion coefficient. Initially, the particles are uniformly distributed in the region $[45, 54]$. Thus, the initial density function is:

$$\rho(x, 0) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{54-45} = \frac{1}{9} & \text{if } 45 \leq x \leq 54, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Periodic boundary conditions imply $\rho(0, t) = \rho(100, t)$ for all t . We expand $\rho(x, t)$ in a Fourier series that respects the periodic boundary conditions:

$$\rho(x, t) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{\rho}_k(t) e^{ik \frac{2\pi}{L} x}$$

where $L = 100$ is the length of the lattice. The initial condition $\rho(x, 0)$ can be expressed as:

$$\rho(x, 0) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{\rho}_k(0) e^{ik \frac{2\pi}{L} x}$$

where the Fourier coefficients are given by:

$$\hat{\rho}_k(0) = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L \rho(x, 0) e^{-ik \frac{2\pi}{L} x} dx$$

Using the initial condition:

$$\hat{\rho}_k(0) = \frac{1}{L} \int_{45}^{54} \frac{1}{9} e^{-ik \frac{2\pi}{L} x} dx$$

Evaluating the integral:

$$\hat{\rho}_k(0) = \frac{1}{9L} \left[\frac{e^{-ik \frac{2\pi}{L} x}}{-ik \frac{2\pi}{L}} \right]_{45}^{54}$$

$$\hat{\rho}_k(0) = \frac{1}{9L} \left(\frac{L}{-ik2\pi} \right) \left(e^{-ik \frac{2\pi}{L} \cdot 54} - e^{-ik \frac{2\pi}{L} \cdot 45} \right)$$

Simplifying:

$$\hat{\rho}_k(0) = \frac{1}{9L} \left(\frac{L}{-ik2\pi} \right) \left(e^{-ik \frac{108\pi}{L}} - e^{-ik \frac{90\pi}{L}} \right)$$

$$\hat{\rho}_k(0) = \frac{n}{9L} \left(\frac{L}{-ik2\pi} \right) \left(e^{-ik \frac{108\pi}{L}} - e^{-ik \frac{90\pi}{L}} \right)$$

Substitute the Fourier series expansion into the diffusion equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{\rho}_k(t) e^{ik \frac{2\pi}{L} x} \right) = D \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left(\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{\rho}_k(t) e^{ik \frac{2\pi}{L} x} \right)$$

The left-hand side becomes:

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d\hat{\rho}_k(t)}{dt} e^{ik\frac{2\pi}{L}x}$$

The right-hand side becomes:

$$D \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{\rho}_k(t) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} e^{ik\frac{2\pi}{L}x}$$

Calculate the second derivative with respect to x :

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} e^{ik\frac{2\pi}{L}x} = - \left(\frac{2\pi k}{L} \right)^2 e^{ik\frac{2\pi}{L}x}$$

Therefore, the right-hand side becomes:

$$D \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{\rho}_k(t) \left(- \left(\frac{2\pi k}{L} \right)^2 e^{ik\frac{2\pi}{L}x} \right) = -D \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2\pi k}{L} \right)^2 \hat{\rho}_k(t) e^{ik\frac{2\pi}{L}x}$$

Equating both sides:

$$\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d\hat{\rho}_k(t)}{dt} e^{ik\frac{2\pi}{L}x} = -D \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2\pi k}{L} \right)^2 \hat{\rho}_k(t) e^{ik\frac{2\pi}{L}x}$$

Since the exponential terms $e^{ik\frac{2\pi}{L}x}$ are linearly independent, we equate the coefficients:

$$\frac{d\hat{\rho}_k(t)}{dt} = -D \left(\frac{2\pi k}{L} \right)^2 \hat{\rho}_k(t)$$

This is a first-order linear differential equation for $\hat{\rho}_k(t)$:

$$\frac{d\hat{\rho}_k(t)}{dt} + D \left(\frac{2\pi k}{L} \right)^2 \hat{\rho}_k(t) = 0$$

The solution to this differential equation is:

$$\hat{\rho}_k(t) = \hat{\rho}_k(0) e^{-D \left(\frac{2\pi k}{L} \right)^2 t}$$

The time evolution of the Fourier coefficients $\hat{\rho}_k(t)$ is given by:

$$\hat{\rho}_k(t) = \hat{\rho}_k(0)e^{-D\left(\frac{2\pi k}{L}\right)^2 t}$$

This shows how each Fourier mode decays exponentially over time, with a rate proportional to k^2 . This decay rate is consistent with the diffusive spreading of the initial density distribution. Therefore:

$$\hat{\rho}_k(t) = \frac{1}{9L} \left(\frac{L}{-ik2\pi} \right) \left(e^{-ik\frac{108\pi}{L}} - e^{-ik\frac{90\pi}{L}} \right) e^{-D\left(\frac{2\pi k}{L}\right)^2 t}$$

The inverse Fourier transform gives:

$$\rho(x, t) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{\rho}_k(t) e^{ik\frac{2\pi}{L}x}$$

At large times, the solution will approximate a Gaussian distribution due to the central limit theorem:

$$\rho(x, t) \approx \frac{n}{\sqrt{4\pi Dt}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-x_0)^2}{4Dt}\right)$$

where x_0 is the mean position of the particles initially.

To show the parabolic curve in the logarithmic scale:

$$\log \rho(x, t) = \log\left(\frac{n}{\sqrt{4\pi Dt}}\right) - \frac{(x-x_0)^2}{4Dt}$$

The logarithm of the Gaussian distribution will be a parabola:

$$\log \rho(x, t) = \text{constant} - \frac{(x-x_0)^2}{4Dt}$$

Therefore, the solution shows a Gaussian nature, and taking the logarithmic value will illustrate a parabolic curve. This analysis follows the physical diffusion process and the initial and boundary conditions provided. In Figures 7 and 8, we plotted the solution with simulation and tried to match the results.

Figure 7: Plot of simulation and analytical solution for N-particle system

Figure 8: logarithmic plots of both cases

3. Result

In this study, we have thoroughly investigated the simple random walk and its interacting variations through both analytical and simulation approaches. Our primary focus was to understand the behavior of random walks, their mathematical formulation, and their implications in physical systems. We first derived the differential equation for the probability distribution of a simple random walk. Using Fourier transforms, we found that the probability distribution function $P(x, t)$ for a simple random walk is Gaussian with a mean of zero and variance proportional to time t . In the discrete form of the random walk was explored using the discrete Laplacian. The resulting difference equation was converted to a differential equation in the continuum limit, confirming that the probability distribution remains Gaussian. In simulation, The deviation from the mean, plotted against time, showed excellent agreement between simulation and theory, confirming the linear relationship between time and variance. Introducing periodic boundaries, the simulations revealed how the system evolves to a steady-state distribution. The steady-state probability density was uniformly distributed, as expected, with a value of $\frac{1}{L}$ for a domain size L .

4. References

References

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Appendix A. Steady-State Concept

The steady-state (or equilibrium state) of a Markov process is a state where the probability distribution $P_j(t)$ no longer changes with time, i.e., $P_j(t+1) = P_j(t)$ for all j . This implies that the system has reached a balance where the probabilities of transitioning between states have reached equilibrium.

From the derived solution:

$$P_j(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \lambda_k^t \hat{P}_k(0) e^{i \frac{2\pi k j}{N}}$$

where

$$\lambda_k = 2p \cos\left(\frac{2\pi k}{N}\right) + 1 - 2p$$

We need to analyze the behavior of λ_k^t as t approaches infinity.

Eigenvalues λ_k

- $\lambda_0 = 1$ (since $\cos(0) = 1$)

- For $k \neq 0$, $|\lambda_k| < 1$ (since $-1 \leq \cos\left(\frac{2\pi k}{N}\right) \leq 1$)

As $t \rightarrow \infty$: - $\lambda_0^t = 1$ - $\lambda_k^t \rightarrow 0$ for $k \neq 0$ because $|\lambda_k| < 1$

Therefore, in the limit as $t \rightarrow \infty$, only the term corresponding to λ_0 survives in the sum, and all other terms decay to zero:

$$P_j(\infty) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \delta_{k,0} \hat{P}_k(0) e^{i \frac{2\pi k j}{N}}$$

Since $\delta_{k,0} = 1$ for $k = 0$ and $\delta_{k,0} = 0$ otherwise, we have:

$$P_j(\infty) = \frac{1}{N} \hat{P}_0(0)$$

Recall that:

$$\hat{P}_0(0) = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} P_j(0) e^{-i \frac{2\pi \cdot 0 \cdot j}{N}} = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} P_j(0) = 1$$

Hence:

$$P_j(\infty) = \frac{1}{N}$$

Figure A.9: Plots of Analytical solution and simulation for single particle in a periodic boundary condition

The steady-state probability distribution is uniform across all sites:

$$P_j(\infty) = \frac{1}{N}$$

This result indicates that, in the long run, the particle is equally likely to be found at any of the N sites. The system reaches a state of maximum entropy, where all sites have the same probability. In the figure below, we have plotted the analytical solution alongside the simulation and checked the plots are matching or not.